

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION TO LEARN FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN FUTURE ENGINEERS

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Abstract. *As a result of large-scale reforms implemented in the higher education system today, it is necessary to introduce an effective system of teaching foreign languages. In addition to the work done, today there is a need to improve the quality of effective and systematic teaching of the English language. In this work, the theoretical basis of increasing the motivation of future engineers to learn foreign languages in technical higher education institutions is discussed.*

Keywords: *higher education, foreign language, internet, information technologies.*

ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ МОТИВАЦИИ К ИЗУЧЕНИЮ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ У БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ

Аннотация. *В результате масштабных реформ, проводимых сегодня в системе высшего образования, необходимо внедрить эффективную систему обучения иностранным языкам. Помимо проделанной работы, на сегодняшний день существует потребность в повышении качества эффективного и системного обучения английскому языку. В данной работе рассматриваются теоретические основы повышения мотивации будущих инженеров к изучению иностранных языков в технических вузах.*

Ключевые слова: *высшее образование, иностранный язык, интернет, информационные технологии.*

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 19, 2021 "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan" PQ-5117 coordinating the introduction of internationally recognized language teaching programs and textbooks at all levels of education and developing modern teaching skills of teachers;

organizing training of foreign languages in high demand based on the results of the analysis of the needs of regions, sectors and educational institutions for specialists who master foreign languages;

coordinating the development of methodologies and recommendations for language learning suitable for all levels of the population in order to introduce a chain of continuous education based on the principle of "kindergarten-school-higher education organization-enterprise" in the field of foreign language teaching;

more serious attention has been paid to the creation of video clips, games, entertainment programs, films and other educational content for thorough mastery of foreign languages, formation of basic language skills.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Resolution No. 312 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 "On measures to effectively organize the popularization of learning foreign languages" also defines the following tasks in order to digitize the teaching of foreign languages and widely introduce modern information and communication technologies in the field:

a) online training courses for young people in foreign languages should be launched in IT centers in the regions, and a part of these costs should be covered by the Youth Fund in accordance with the procedure established by the law.

The Ministry of Information Technology and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan should approve the plan of measures for the organization of online training courses involving foreign specialists in IT centers within two months;

b) licensing procedures of educational organizations organizing the educational process on the basis of distance (online) teaching technologies should be simplified, taking into account the following:

revising the terms of the educational organization regarding educational tools and defining special requirements for distance (online) teaching technologies;

formation of legal bases for organization of educational process on the basis of recognized foreign and international standards;

taking into account the possibility of conducting the educational process remotely (online) through automated programs and video courses;

to create an opportunity to involve persons with practical skills as well as pedagogic personnel in the educational process, including in the field of information and communication technologies.

There are several pedagogical studies on improving the system of teaching foreign language (English) in technical higher education institutions of our republic. However, there is a need for systematic research that fully covers the main components of creating a teaching system based on innovative technologies for technical higher education institutions in the subject of foreign language (English). In this sense, our republic demands to improve the content of creating a teaching system based on innovative technologies for technical higher education institutions and to revise the existing teaching methods and technologies.

In today's rapidly developing technological society, the need for highly skilled and professional professionals is increasing. Uzbekistan has clearly defined the criteria for entering the global educational space and is modernizing the education system in accordance with international requirements. The driving force of the innovative processes taking place in Uzbekistan's higher education institutions is the desire to adapt to the domestic labor market and become a full member of the world education system. We must constantly adapt educational programs to the requirements of the labor market. The quality criterion determines readiness for practical activities and real competitiveness of graduates.

The main goal of learning a foreign language is the formation of foreign language competence, all other goals (learning, training, development) are implemented in the process of realizing this main goal.

RESULTS

By analyzing scientific research works, it can be said that many scientists have singled out foreign language competence as the main competence in their classifications. But it can be said that the level of knowledge of foreign languages of the pedagogic staff trained for engineering in technical higher educational institutions by the scientists of our country has not been studied as a pedagogical problem.

Teaching a foreign language means teaching communication, information transfer and perception. There are three directions for bringing the teaching of foreign languages to a new

level on the Internet, including in the information educational environment: communication, information and publication. Communication is carried out by e-mail, large layers of information are placed on the world wide web.

DISCUSSION

As an information system, the Internet offers its users a variety of information and resources. The main set of services includes: e-mail; newsgroups; video conferences; the ability to publish your personal information, create your own personal page and place it on a web server; access to information sources: information directories (yahoo!, ultrasmart, look smart, galaxy); search engines (altawesta, hotbob, open text, Websrawler); online chat (chat). These resources can be actively used in the lesson.

We know that in language learning, students can improve their vocabulary in addition to working on their reading and speaking skills. To do this, it is necessary to invite the future engineer to compile dictionary articles based on the information he has read. The result of this work may be the creation of its own page dedicated to one specific event, where it is necessary to try to look at the problem neutrally based on the analysis of information from various news agencies. In order to develop intercultural competence, there are advantages of researching articles devoted to a certain topic of only one news agency for a long time: by studying the problem in depth, the future engineer can not only determine the position of a certain country in relation to the problem under study, but also learn the basis of such a point of view, and accordingly, will be able to predict the development of events. After the completed work, a discussion or tele-conference is necessary, in which the work of each student or group will be a separate branch of the common problem, that is, they will have the opportunity to share their results and combine them into a whole.

CONCLUSIONS

To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop appropriate behavior. And this can be done with the help of new technologies, in particular, the Internet.

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